

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Postpartum external factors associated with the development of Todler wasting in Indonesia

Febri Theresia Sihaloho ^{1,*}, Desmawati Desmawati ² and Bobby Indra Utama ³

¹ Master of Midwifery Program, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Andalas, Indonesia.

² Department of Nutrition Science, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Andalas, Indonesia.

³ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Andalas, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Development results from a maturation process that includes gross motor, fine motor, cognitive, and language abilities. The percentage of children under five whose growth and development are monitored in Indonesia is 69.6% and has not yet reached the target of the Indonesian Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan 2021, namely 70%. This research aims to identify factors related to toddler development in Indonesia. This research was a narrative literature review. A literature search was conducted using PubMed and Google databases to identify articles published within eight years (2016-2023). The keywords used to search for this article are parenting, stimulation, income, exclusive breastfeeding, and development. This research involved an assessment of 17 articles from Indonesia regarding factors related to toddler development. Based on the study, factors related to toddler development are stimulation, parenting style, family income, and history of exclusive breastfeeding. Health workers are expected to be able to provide education on how to provide stimulation, implement good parenting patterns, and provide good nutrition for the development of toddlers.

Keywords: Parenting Style; Stimulation; Income; Exclusive Breastfeeding; Development.

1. Introduction

Development is an increase in the capacity for more complex body structures and functions as a result of the maturation process, which includes gross motor, fine motor, cognitive, and language abilities, which can be formed through environmental interactions, especially in the first five years of a toddler's life (1). Malnutrition (wasting) is a nutritional condition of children under five characterized by being thin due to disease and acute or chronic lack of nutritional intake. The index used is weight according to body length or height less than -3 to -2 standard deviations in toddlers (2,3). Toddlers who suffer from wasting (malnutrition) will have a weak immune system and will, of course, be susceptible to developmental delays, disease, and even death (4). By 2030, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) target in point 4.2 guarantees that all girls and boys have access to quality essential preschool development, care, and education to be ready to receive primary education (5).

As many as 250 million children (43%) under five in low- and middle-income countries are at risk of not reaching their developmental potential (6). In Indonesia in 2021, the percentage of children under five whose growth and development were monitored was 69.6% and had not yet reached the target of the Indonesian Ministry of Health's Strategic Plan for 2021, namely 70% (7). The index proportion and type of development of children aged 36-59 months is 85.2%, with numeracy literacy at 58.1%, physical ability at 97.4%, social-emotional ability at 66%, and learning ability at 96.1% (8). External factors related to toddler development are income, parenting and stimulation patterns, and history of exclusive breastfeeding (1). Wasting nutritional status is a risk factor for delays in children's growth and development and increases the risk by 3.5 times for experiencing delays in children's growth and development (9).

* Corresponding author: Desmawati

Based on the description above, researchers are interested in studying postnatal external factors related to toddler development.

2. Literature Review

Development is an increase in the capacity for more complex body structures and functions as a result of the maturation process, which includes gross motor, fine motor, cognitive, and language abilities, which can be formed through environmental interactions, especially in the first five years of a toddler's life (1). Toddlers who suffer from wasting (malnutrition) will have a weak immune system and will, of course, be susceptible to developmental delays, disease, and even death (4). External factors related to toddler development are income, parenting style, stimulation, and history of exclusive breastfeeding.

Families who have adequate income can help support children's growth and development. Families who have sufficient income are likely to be able to provide children with games that can stimulate their growth and development. Families with low economic status can be seen from the monthly income the family generates to meet the family's needs. Low family income affects the provision of food to their children by families. Families with low incomes tend to have limited education and a lack of family ability to provide the means to stimulate their children's development. This gives rise to an eternal cycle of poverty/a prolonged cycle of poverty that affects poor child development (10).

Parenting is a method and effort of parents to care for and guide their children consistently to form character and personality and provide values for children to adapt to their environment (11). Each parent has a different way of raising their child, including parenting styles. Parental treatment of children can contribute considerably to the child's social, emotional, and intellectual competence (12).

Stimulation is an effort to make children smarter by stimulating children's fundamental abilities so that every child needs to receive routine stimulation as early as possible and continuously at every opportunity (1,13). The aim is to help children achieve optimal development according to the child's developmental stages, including cognitive development, language development, social, emotional, and motor skills (14).

Exclusive breast milk is fluid or milk produced from the mother's breast glands in the form of natural, nutritious, and high-energy food (15). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), exclusive breastfeeding is breast milk given to babies from birth until six months old without providing complementary foods/drinks or substitutes other than breast milk except for medicines and vitamin or mineral drops. Breastfeeding can help protect children from various diseases, increase intelligence quotient (IQ), and encourage a strong bond between mother and baby (16).

3. Material and methods

This research was a narrative review. A literature searched by using PubMed and Google Scholar to identify articles published over eight years (2016-2023). The keywords used in this literature search are stimulation, parenting style, income, exclusive breastfeeding, and development.

4. Results

This research involved an assessment of 17 research articles regarding developmental factors in toddlers obtained from Pub-Med and Google databases.

Table 1 Research articles

No	Author	Research Title	Country	Method	Factors Associated with Toddler Development
	Wiguna AA and Tridiyawati F, 2022 (12)	The Influence of Parenting Patterns on Child Development (Pengaruh Pola Asuh Orang Tua Terhadap Perkembangan Anak)	Indonesia	Cross Sectional	Parenting

Barir B and Fatmawati Z, 2020 (17)	The Effect of Exclusive Breastfeeding and Stimulation on the Development of Toddlers Aged 1-2 Years in Momby Kid Jombang (Pengaruh Asi Eksklusif dan Stimulasi Terhadap Perkembangan Balita Usia 1-2 Tahun Di Momby Kid Jombang)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Exclusive breastfeeding, Stimulation
Maemunah S and Sari RS, 2022 (18)	Exclusive Breast Milk for The Growth and Development of Babies Aged 1-6 Months (ASI Eksklusif Dengan Pertumbuhan Dan Perkembangan Bayi Usia 1-6 Bulan)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Exclusive breastfeeding
Mariyanah and Syarah M, 2022 (19)	The Relationship between Knowledge, Parenting Patterns and History of Exclusive Breastfeeding with the Development of Toddlers in the Curug Community Health Center Work Area in 2022 (Hubungan Pengetahuan, Pola Asuh dan Riwayat Asi Eksklusif dengan Perkembangan Balita di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Curug Tahun 2022)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Parenting pattern, history of exclusive breastfeeding
Siagian DS and Herlina S, 2019 (20)	Analysis of the Relationship between Exclusive Breastfeeding and Mother's Education on Baby Development (Analisis Hubungan Pemberian Asi Eksklusif Dan Pendidikan Ibu Terhadap Perkembangan Bayi)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Exclusive breastfeeding, maternal education
Hati FS and Lestari P, 2016 (21)	The Effect of Providing Stimulation on the Development of Children Aged 12-36 Months in Sedayu District, Bantul (Pengaruh Pemberian Stimulasi Pada Perkembangan Anak Usia 12-36 Bulan Di Kecamatan Sedayu, Bantul)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Stimulation
Mustikaningrum AC and Munawaroh S, 2021 (22)	The Relationship Between Nutritional Status and Parenting Patterns and the Development Level of Toddlers Aged 4-5 Years in Sukorejo District, Kendal Regency (Hubungan Antara Status Gizi Dan Pola Asuh Dengan Tingkat Perkembangan Balita Usia 4-5 Tahun Di Kecamatan Sukorejo Kabupaten Kendal)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Nutritional status, parenting style
Batubara AR and Mona, 2020 (23)	The Relationship between Exclusive Breastfeeding and Psychosocial Stimulation with Toddler Development in Meunasah Dayah Village, Kota Juang District, Bireuen Regency (Hubungan Pemberian Asi Eksklusif Dan Stimulasi Psikososial Dengan Perkembangan Balita Di Desa Meunasah Dayah Kecamatan Kota Juang Kabupaten Bireuen)	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Exclusive breastfeeding, psychosocial stimulation
Murdiningsih and Komariah N, 2019 (25)	Knowledge and parenting patterns with toddler's growth and development	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Mother's knowledge, parenting style
Amir NAR <i>et al.</i> , 2019 (26)	Factors Associated with Development in Children Under Five	Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Maternal age during pregnancy, asphyxia, birth

					weight, family income
	Jayanti N <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (27)	Factors Affecting Toddlers' Development in Pamekasan Regency	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	Maternal age at marriage, stimulation, birth weight
	Safaringga M <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (29)	The Relationship Between Parenting And Development of Toddlers Aged 1-5 Years in The Working Area of Rawang Public Health Center, Padang City	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	Parenting
	Hayuningtyas RD <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (30)	Analysis of Factors Affecting the Development of Children of Toddler Ages Assessed from History of Infection Diseases, Nutritional Status and Psychosocial Stimulation in Ponorogo Regency	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	History of infectious diseases, nutritional status, psychosocial stimulation
	Rachmawatie DA <i>et al.</i> , 2022 (31)	Analysis of Factors Affecting the Development Status of Toddlers in Simomulyo Health Center Surabaya	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	History of exclusive breastfeeding
	Andriyani R <i>et al.</i> , 2023 (33)	Factors Affecting the Developmental Status of Children Aged 6 Months to 2 Years in Urban and Rural Areas	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	Child's age, exposure to screen time, stimulation, nutritional status, and use of KIA books
	Khairani N <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (34)	Family Income Level, Parenting Patterns, Development Stimulation, And Toddler Development (Tingkat Pendapatan Keluarga, Pola Asuh Orang Tua Stimulasi Perkembangan Dan Perkembangan Balita)	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	Parenting style, stimulation
	Krisdiantini A <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (35)	The Relationship Between Parenting Patterns and Child Development at Preschool Age	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	Parenting

5. Discussion

Based on a literature review, the factors that play a role in toddler development are:

5.1. Stimulation

Parental stimulation is part of a child's nurturing needs (13). Stimulation is carried out by parents or family at every opportunity or daily and is adjusted to the child's age without ignoring stimulation principles. This means that stimulation is given according to the level or phase of the child's psychological development to avoid damage to the next phase (36). The results of Damarini's research showed that the results of the development assessment of 263 children contained possible deviations (score six or <6) in the development of 8 children and doubtful development (score 7 – 8) in 30 children (37). This occurs due to a lack of appropriate and correct stimulation to children, which will cause deviations in the child's growth and development and persistent disorders (1). In line with other research, there is a relationship between stimulation and toddler development (17). The stimulation efforts should be carried out by paying attention to the child's growth stages to make the results more effective. Stimulation during the critical period occurs in the first 1000 days of life. Motor development can be improved through the relationship between mother and child, providing physical exercise and early stimulation (21).

5.2. Parenting Styles

Parenting patterns include daily activities by parents or caregivers to protect children, care for them, fulfill their needs, and support their growth and development. Proper care will encourage children to reach their optimal potential (1).

The parenting style carried out by parents is the best way to educate their children as a form of responsibility towards their children. Parenting patterns will influence children differently, so appropriate parenting patterns will enable children to interact with the surrounding environment (25). However, some parents sometimes don't realize what kind of parenting style they are implementing. Parenting is crucial in shaping a child's behavior and intelligence. Parental treatment of children can contribute considerably to the child's social, emotional, and intellectual competence (12). In line with other research, there is a relationship between parenting styles and toddler development (29). Research conducted by Dahlan shows that children with negative parenting patterns have 12 times the risk of experiencing developmental disorders compared to children under five with positive parenting patterns (38).

5.3. Family Income

One of the shapes of a family's lifestyle is economic status. Adequate family income will help children's growth and development because parents are responsible for all children's growth and development needs, both primary and secondary. Income dramatically influences purchasing power, and the interaction between socio-cultural factors influences consumption behavior. Economic considerations influence income levels and control purchasing power (39). The level of wealth will determine the quality and quantity of food. The quality and quantity of the diet that applies in a family is related to the size of the family and the size of the family income (40). This aligns with Amir's research that a relationship exists between family income and toddler development (26). Other researchers also found a relationship between family income and the growth and development of toddlers. This could be because the income received can be entirely spent on basic food needs. A high income level can guarantee good nutritional status for toddlers (41).

5.4. History of exclusive breastfeeding

Exclusive breastfeeding is defined as breastfeeding without supplementation with food or drink other than medication. After six months, breast milk cannot meet the needs of minerals such as iron and zinc, so to meet these needs, MPASI (complementary foods for breast milk), which are rich in iron, must be given (42). Every mother who gives birth must provide exclusive breast milk to the baby she gives birth to. However, this does not apply if there are medical indications that the mother is absent or separated from the baby (43). The benefits of exclusive breastfeeding are increasing the baby's body resistance, especially against disease, and helping the baby's brain and physical development (44). Belfield's research explains that breastfeeding can increase the probability that children will be healthier and prevent obesity. In addition, breastfeeding for six months or more can improve gross motor development by the time the child is nine months old (45). Siagian's research states a relationship between exclusive breastfeeding and infant development with an OR value of 5.23, meaning that mothers who do not exclusively breastfeed are 5.23 times more likely to have stunted baby development than mothers who exclusively breastfeed (20).

6. Conclusion

Factors related to toddler development are stimulation, parenting patterns, family income, and history of exclusive breastfeeding. Efforts made to monitor the development of toddlers are by providing education on how to provide stimulation, implementing good parenting patterns, and fulfilling reasonable nutrition requirements for toddler development.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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